

Some Aspects of the Chemistry of Lac-Resin†

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The native lac-resin was fractionated to a consistent hard-resin fraction which was subjected separately to periodate fission, permanganate oxidation, borohydride reduction and hydrazinolysis. The statistical results are described. The substitution of the hydroxyl function by halogen of the primary terpene acids is also described.

Lac-resin¹, the processed form of which called shellac is a product of importance to India, interwoven with its culture and history for a long time, from the days of Mahabharata. Its utilization, along with the colouring matter and wax secreted by the insect *Laccifer lacca* (Kerr.), growing wild and infesting the forests of Madhya Pradesh, Orissa, Bihar and Bengal (what is now currently the 'Jharkhand' area) had been widespread for a long time. It is to the genius of ancient Indian people, to have recognized its utility even at the dawn of history, using the colouring matter for dyeing cotton and silk and the resin for making bangles, jewellery boxes etc., apart from their general use in polishes for wooden surface. After thousands of years, these products have survived in the world market and it is an important export commodity of value even today.

The chemistry of lac-resin has been investigated the world over for over seventy years and lot of details are known today. However, as will be pointed out later, further utilization of this material is still possible in several directions.

The resin is a very complex mixture and not separable readily into the pure components. Further, the composition of the resin mixture varies extensively depending upon the host trees, period of collection, mode of storage and other environmental factors. Early work² conducted in India usually separated the resin mixture through solvent extraction. The consistency of this procedure was always doubtful because of the property of the resin to swell in contact with solvents forming a gel as the solvent never penetrated the swollen mass successfully and completely. The total resin consists of a complex mixture of long-chain free fatty acids, saturated, unsaturated and hydroxylated as well as alcohols. It also contains some of these acids esterified with sesquiterpene acids of the cedrene skeleton and the desirable properties of shellac originate from this combination. The molecular weight of some of the ester fractions usually range around 1800–2500.

An alkaline hydrolysis² of the resin yields the main hydroxy fatty acids, aleuritic acid (1) and butolic acid⁶ (2). Sesquiterpene acids like shellolic^{3a} (3), 2-*epi*-shellolic^{3a} (4),

jalaric^{3b} (5), laccijalaric^{3b} (6) and 2-*epi*-laksholic^{3b} (7) acids are also formed

Sukh Dev and his group^{3b} established the structure of many of these terpene acids and projected a structure (8) for a pure fraction of the resin, which they reported.

On the possibilities of utilization of aleuritic acid in the synthesis of perfumery products and pheromones, we have carried out an extensive investigation during the past two decades and the results are summarised in a review⁴.

Realising the complexity of the resin as mentioned earlier, we attempted a fractional precipitation⁵ of the resin rather than a fractional extraction. The total resin is soluble in cold alcohol and a large part of the low molecular weight components are soluble in diethyl ether. This difference has been utilized by early workers^{1,2} to separate the resin into two major fractions. The more polymerized fraction was known as hard-resin (since this fraction was a hard, brittle mass). The ether soluble fraction was a viscous mass carrying all the low molecular weight compounds either as inter-esters or free acids. However, the early workers used a pro-

†Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

8 R = CHO/COOH, R¹ = CH₂OH/CH₃

cedure of fractional extraction and not fractional precipitation. Using the fractional precipitation we were able to obtain a consistent hard-resin fraction which was free from the complicating fractions. Later a similar procedure was adopted by Sukh Dev^{3b} and his group in order to get their pure hard-resin.

The pure reproducible fraction of ours was then subjected to a series of experiments. It is known from the work⁶ of Gunstone that only aleuritic acid (1) is the main C₁₆ fatty acid with the presence of the C₁₄ acid butolic acid (2) to a much smaller extent. The pure fraction obtained by the above process of good consistency was treated with hydriodic acid⁷, followed by reduction with zinc-amalgam and acid to give the saturated fatty acids. Gas-liquid chromatography⁸ of the methyl ester mixture clearly showed that our hard-resin fraction contained the C₁₆ : C₁₄ in the ratio of 6 : 1 as methyl palmitate and methyl myristate respectively. When all the C₁₆ chain is primarily in the form of aleuritic acid, this gives an estimate of the aleuritic acid content as nearly 40% of the hard-resin. During this process the role and the extent of the terpenes was ignored.

In another set of experiments, an oxidative degradation⁹ of this hard-resin fraction was undertaken. After several trials with different oxidizing agents, potassium permanganate in acetone-acetic acid solution was chosen for this purpose. Under these conditions esters and acetals were stable. The fate of the terpene acids during this series of experiments was ignored. It can be readily seen that all the four functionalities of aleuritic acid can participate simultaneously in the esterification process or else some of them may be left free. The extent to which each centre of aleuritic acid participates in this resin fraction is therefore analyzable. It may be brought to the notice that this hard-resin fraction does not contain any uncombined aleuritic acid. Our experiments¹⁰ as well as that of others, through a periodate fission of the hard-resin indicate that nearly half the quan-

tity of aleuritic acid has the 1,2-glycol function free. The remaining part of the glycol is involved in some kind of linkage.

With this background the hard-resin was subjected to permanganate oxidation⁹ in acetone-acetic acid solution to give the water-soluble acid-components and a viscous gummy product. Scheme 1 indicates the sequence of separations performed and the inferences drawn are as follows. (i) Half of the total available aleuritic acid has its vicinal hydroxyls free. (ii) All the alkali hydrolysable aleuritic acid units are broken down by potassium permanganate. (iii) Most of the aleuritic acid units are only partially linked. (iv)

Scheme 1

All the four active centres of aleuritic acid are not involved in ester links at the same time. (v) The presence of alkali-stable links in the resin is confirmed. (vi) Alkali-stable links involved mainly the 9- or 10-hydroxyls (or both) of aleuritic acid. (vii) The end hydroxyl group at C₁₆ is predominantly free.

The structure projected by Sukh Dev^{3b}, for his pure fraction subsequently is amenable for incorporation of some of the above conclusions.

The hard-resin contains the terpene acids primarily in the form of the aldehydic acid (5). This acid creates numerous obstacles during degradation and characterization of the products. Sukh Dev and his group¹¹ elaborated this aspect extensively and effectively. However, configurational purity at C-2 under alkaline conditions becomes doubtful. We carried out a set of experiments to avoid some of these problems. The hard-resin being soluble in methanol, a borohydride reduction was feasible, leading to the conversion of the aldehyde function at C-2 into CH₂OH. This reduction does not affect free carboxyl groups. No epimerization at C-2 was noticed during such reductions. Therefore the hard-resin was reduced with borohydride¹² followed by an alkaline hydrolysis. All the jalaric acid present in the resin was recovered in the form of 2-*epi*-laksholic acid (7). Interestingly, 2-*epi*-shellolic acid was isolated to the same extent to which it was isolated by a direct alkaline hydrolysis (20% NaOH) prior to the borohydride reduction. This clearly demonstrates that the parent resin is made up of some units of 2-*epi*-shellolic acid (4). Further, a highly increased yield of 2-*epi*-laksholic acid indicates that all aldehydic acids present in the resin had the 2-*epi*-geometry. This reduction demonstrates that the isolation of shellolic acid as the main product in the direct alkaline hydrolysis (20% NaOH) of the hard resin is the result of Cannizzaro reaction as suggested by Sukh Dev, thus ending up giving a substantial yield of shellolic and 2-*epi*-laksholic acids as the primary products, the 2-*epi*-shellolic acid being present in the native resin itself. All the above data can be summarized through the following main conclusions. (i) The terpene acids in their native state in the resin are to be found with 2-*epi*-geometry. (ii) Shellolic acid itself results as a consequence of the alkaline hydrolysis. (iii) 2-*epi*-Shellolic acid does have an independent existence in the resin side by side with 2-*epi*-jalaric acid and participates in the resin formation.

It is very likely that further fractionation of our hard resin may lead to components of higher purity and such a pure component has indeed been isolated by Sukh Dev and his group which has the structure 8. It will be realized that our assessment of the gross picture includes the points of linkages possessed by the component subsequently isolated and characterized by Sukh Dev and his group. Clearly, the gross

picture indicates that the hard-resin may carry individual components which do not fully stick to the pattern of structure 8. This is indicated by the product composition during other degradations as described below.

One aspect of the oxidation experiments has not been elaborated so far. The isolation of 9,10-dihydroxyhexadec-1,16-dioic acid in the oxidation experiments (Scheme 1) and not a ketol indicates that the 9,10-hydroxyl group is simultaneously blocked to some extent. We believe, that some part of the 1,2-glycol function of aleuritic acid is present in the form of dioxolane, thereby the aldehyde of jalaric acid taking part in the process of dioxolane formation. It is well known that acetalization is an equilibrium reaction and that a dioxolane is more stable than open chain acetals. In the equilibrium both the free aldehyde and the cyclic acetal survive. Hence the periodate fission¹³ will be an index of the extent of acetalization as well.

All the experimental procedures revolve around an alkaline hydrolysis under different conditions. We have recently made an effort to look for an alternative procedure which would throw more light on the structural features of the hard-resin. In order to fulfil this objective we investigated a hydrazinolysis of the hard-resin.

Prior to this attempt, we prepared the hydrazides of the three main acids of hard-resin, namely, aleuritic acid (1), shellolic acid (3) and 2-*epi*-shellolic acid (4). It is relevant to point out here that the manufacturing process of aleuritic acid invariably involves a high concentration of alkali and the terpene acids are always recovered as shellolic (3), *epi*-shellolic (4) and 2-*epi*-laksholic (7) acids, the jalaric acid (5) failing to survive these conditions. During such a hydrolysis, the manufacturers either discard the gummy fraction or sell it off for a low price for such industries in need of this material. It should be borne in mind that this discarded terpene fraction is capable of providing value added products of importance.

The hydrazides of shellolic¹⁴, *epi*-shellolic and aleuritic acids are capable of being formed from a mixture of all the three as well as individually. All the three give crystalline hydrazides, the dihydrazide in the case of shellolic and *epi*-shellolic acids and a monohydrazide in case of aleuritic acid. However, hydrazide formation with 2-*epi*-shellolic and shellolic acids in presence of aqueous hydrazine does not take place. The corresponding esters readily form the hydrazides. Interestingly, their solubility properties are quite different. While shellolic dihydrazide is very sparingly soluble in water, that of aleuritic hydrazide is moderately soluble and 2-*epi*-shellolic dihydrazide is the most soluble of the three. It was therefore possible through a careful fractionation to separate all the three hydrazides. These hydrazides are then readily hydrolyzed to the corresponding

acids by 8% aqueous alkali. The lac-resin primarily has ester links. Hydrazinolysis of these ester links in hard-resin should therefore be feasible.

As model experiments, hydrazinolysis of dimethyl-10,13-di-*O*-acetyl shellolate (9) was carried out when shellolic dihydrazide and acetic hydrazide were obtained. Similarly, dimethyl-13-*O*-stearoyl shellolate (10)^{15,16} on hydrazinolysis gave shellolic dihydrazide and stearic hydrazide. Hydrazinolysis of dimethyl-13-(9,10,16-triacetyl)-*O*-aleuritoyl shellolate (11) and dimethyl-10,13-di(9,10,16-triacetyl)-*O*-aleuritoyl shellolate¹⁷ (12) gave shellolic dihydrazide, aleuritic hydrazide and acetic hydrazide.

Encouraged by the feasibility, we subjected our hard-resin to a process of hydrazinolysis. Our hard-resin contains several free carboxyl functions, shown by its solubility in alkali. It was therefore expected that aqueous hydrazine (50%) in methanol solution will dissolve the resin readily. The free carboxyl function may be converted into the corresponding hydrazinium salt. The free aldehyde under the conditions employed does not form a hydrazone. Those carboxyl functions which are in the esterified state, no matter whether they belong to aleuritic acid or that of 2-*epi*-shellolic acid or of 2-*epi*-jalaric acid should be susceptible to hydrazinolysis resulting in that unit carrying the esterified carboxyl appearing as the corresponding hydrazide and the unit carrying the esterified hydroxyl released as such. We can look for, after the hydrazinolysis, aleuritic hydrazide where its corresponding acid function had been esterified with an alcoholic function of the terpene acid; *epi*-shellolic dihydrazide where both the carboxyl functions had been esterified with an alcoholic function of aleuritic acid; 2-*epi*-

shellolic monohydrazide where only one of the carboxyls had been esterified; 2-*epi*-jalaric hydrazide where the carboxyl group of jalaric acid had been esterified. For the purpose of isolation and characterisation, the reaction mixture may have to be brought to a suitable pH in order to break up the hydrazinium salts. Taking into account the above factors, aliquot portions of the reaction mixture were brought to different pH levels and each portion was extracted with organic solvents, like ethyl acetate. The non-hydrazide fractions of the organic extracts were then esterified using standard procedures and the components separated by column chromatography. This resulted in the isolation of dimethyl 2-*epi*-shellolate, dimethyl acetal of 2-*epi*-jalarate, methyl aleuritate and surprisingly very minor quantity of methyl 2-*epi*-laksholate as well. This indicates that the hard-resin fraction contains the above components whose alcoholic function was utilized in ester formation. From among the hydrazide fractions only aleuritic hydrazide was obtained pure as a crystalline solid, being the major component. It clearly indicates the role of aleuritic acid whose carboxyl participated in a primary way in ester formation with hydroxyls of the terpene acids.

The terpene hydrazides were present in the mixture however as a complex mixture as well as being secondary to presence of aleuritic hydrazide. The inference would be that the acid function of the terpene participates much less in forming esters with the alcoholic group of aleuritic acid. All the above results indicate that one may expect the presence of numerous structural variations in the hard-resin. The only confirmed and reliable conclusions one can draw from the available data on lac-resin are as follows. (i) The terpenes participating in resin formation have 2-*epi* configuration. (ii) 2-*epi*-Shellolic acid also participates in resin formation. (iii) Shellolic acid is formed primarily during alkaline hydrolysis. (iv) The carboxyl of aleuritic acid is extensively utilized for ester formation. (v) The fraction reported by Sukh Dev^{3b} is likely to be one of the components present in lac-resin and the other components may structurally differ from it substantially. (vi) The isolation of aleuritic acid during hydrazinolysis indicates the use of its hydroxyl in ester formation (*cf.* structure 8).

We have brought to the attention of the readers that the manufacturing process of a aleuritic acid discards a massive quantity of the terpenes as an intractable gum. This can be of an order of several tonnes. We have also made attempts to see whether we can isolate these terpenes in a more homogeneous form. One obvious route will be to remove the hydroxyl functions to get a less oxygenated cedrene derivative. The obvious routes will be to substitute the hydroxyl function with halogen and subsequently replace it

with hydrogen. A preliminary step in this direction is to study the reactions of the two primary lac acids 3 and 4. Both these compounds¹⁸ as their methyl esters were then subjected to a reaction with triphenyl phosphine in carbon tetrachloride.

Dimethyl shellolate when treated with excess triphenyl phosphine in dry carbon tetrachloride gave one major product along with two minor slower moving products as observed on tlc. The column chromatography over silica gel yielded the dichloro compound as the major product (*m/z* 360, 362, 364). The spectral analysis of the product showed it to be dimethyl-10 α ,13-dichloroshellolate¹⁸ (ir, nmr and C, H analysis; cf. Ref¹⁹). The two minor products were identified as the two expected monochloro products (mass, ir, nmr) and was not pursued further. The corresponding dimethyl-10 α ,13-dichloro-2-*epi*-shellolate was also prepared¹⁸ following a similar procedure and the structure was indicated by spectral analysis. It was not obtained as a solid and was characterized as the corresponding diacid by an alkaline hydrolysis (ir, nmr, mass and C, H analysis).

The above account gives a clear perspective that several aspects of the resin chemistry can still be pursued profitably and investigations towards proper utilization of the discarded terpenes is highly beneficial for the chemists as well as the shellac industry. It is hoped that this article may catalyze further research activities on lac-resin which is of a high degree of socioeconomic importance to our country.

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